

On the Study of Tetrahydrated Double Sulphate of Tervalent Elements with Radioactive Indicators. Part III

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Distribution studies with $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Ti}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as hosts and Sc^{46} , In^{114} , Fe^{55+59} , $\text{Eu}^{153,154}$, Tb^{160} , Tm^{170} , Y^{90} and Bi^{210} as guests have been studied in considerable details. The former host takes up scandium, indium and ferric iron through mixed crystal formation, and in case of rare earths yttrium and bismuth as guests partition values are negligibly small and the uptake follows an adsorption pattern. In case of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host, Tb^{160} , Tm^{170} , Y^{90} and Bi^{210} tracers are taken up through mixed crystal formation. Sc^{46} , In^{114} and Fe^{55+59} tracers are taken up by the same host through adsorption. Study gives a clear evidence on the existence of two series of tetrahydrated double sulphates of the trivalent elements. Tetrahydrated double sulphate of aluminium, scandium, indium, ferric iron and thallic thallium fall into one group and rare earths and rare earth analogues like yttrium and bismuth fall into another group.

Tetrahydrated double sulphate of scandium has been studied in considerable details. Its transition temperature has been found to be near about 5° . It has been observed that it is metastable with respect to the anhydrous double sulphate. A sample of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Ti}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ containing ~ 14 mol% of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been isolated. All experimental operations were done at 3° .

The distribution coefficient was independent of guest ion concentration in case of scandium and indium, whereas in case of Fe^{55+59} as guest, a rise in values of distribution coefficients was observed with increase in guest ion concentration. A preparation of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Ti}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ containing ~ 11.4 mol% of ferric iron has been isolated. The guest component corroborates a composition similar to that of the host. From experimental evidences it has been argued that disulphate ion of the guest component exchanges with that of the host in the process of uptake.

In a previous communication¹ it has been pointed out that all trivalent elements do not form alum. It was argued that the formation of tetrahydrated double sulphate may be a characteristic feature of all trivalent cations. A glance at the literature will however show that the number of tetrahydrated double sulphates prepared up to date are rather small. Existence of this series in case of trivalent elements from aluminium to thallic thallium including the rare earths and actinides have been claimed though a few of them have been prepared and morphological characters in cases of lanthanum², cerium^{3(ous)}, thallium^{4(ic)} and plutonium^{5(III)}

1. B. C. Purkayastha and D. K. Bhattacharyya, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, No. 10.
2. E. H. Kraus, *Zeit. Kryst.*, 34, 3901; ueber einige Salze der Settenen, Erden, Leipzig (1901).
3. W. Schroder, E. Kehren and K. Frings, *Z.anorg.allgem. Chem*; 1938, 238, 209-24.
4. J. W. Mellor, "A Comprehensive treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry" p-469 Vol-V, (1956).
5. Seaborg and Katz. "Actinide elements" p. 804-809 (1954)

have only been described. It is of interest to note that tetrahydrated double sulphates of each of these four types are monoclinic prisms, but axial ratios in case of thallic thallium differ very much from the other three. Existence of tetrahydrated double sulphate of aluminium was shown⁶ by observing overgrowth on thallic thallium. From these few observations it can be inferred that most of the tervalent cations may form tetrahydrated double sulphates. Failure in their isolation may probably be due to the existence of other hydrates or even anhydrous components which may be the more stable or insoluble phase in question.

Radioactive isotopes of most of the tervalent elements are available and it is quite possible to study the existence of compounds which have not been described through mixed crystal formation. Extent of morphological analogy may also be visualised through such study. With these objects in view, distribution studies with tetrahydrated double sulphate of cerous cerium and thallic thallium as hosts and radioisotopes of scandium, indium, ferric iron, yttrium, bismuth, europium, terbium and thulium as guests have been undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sc⁴⁶ in sulphuric acid and carrier free RaD as lead nitrate in 2.5*N* HNO₃ in equilibrium with RaE (Bi²¹⁰) were supplied by Phillips Duphar. Eu^{152,154} was procured from A. E. R. E. Harwell, England and Tb¹⁶⁰, Tm¹⁷⁰, Y⁹⁰, In¹¹⁴ and Fe^{55,59} from A. E. E. T., India. Natural scandium, indium, terbium, thulium, yttrium and bismuth were of specpure quality and procured from Messrs. Johnson Matthey & Co. Limited, England. Ceric sulphate and ammonium sulphate were of G. R. E. Merck quality. All other reagents used in the investigation were of Analar variety.

Processing of radioactive isotopes and crystallisation of (NH₄)Ce(SO₄)₂.4H₂O in different fractions from 3*N*.H₂SO₄ etc. have already been described in our previous communications^{1,7}. It was found that even in case of low degree of supersaturation time required for complete breakdown of supersaturation requires twenty hours. Distribution study was carried out by taking 4.62 gms of ammonium sulphate and 50 ml. of cerous sulphate solution (1.4 × 10⁻¹ M in 3*N*.H₂SO₄) in series of L-shaped tubes containing different quantities of 3*N*.H₂SO₄ and activity in question placed in the thermostat at 15° and shaking for 24 hrs. A portion of the solution from each of the tubes was then taken out and activity was measured by a liquid counter. Cerium was estimated as CeO₂. Homogeneous distribution

6. Fortini and Piccini, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1902, **31**, 451.

7. B. C. Purkayastha and D. K. Bhattacharyya, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1963, Vol. 96, No. 5-6.

factor (D) and heterogeneous distribution factor (λ) were calculated from the following expressions^{8,9}.

$$D = \frac{\left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}}\right)_{\text{solid}}}{\left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}}\right)_{\text{solution}}}$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\log \frac{\text{Initial tracer}}{\text{Tracer in solution}}}{\log \frac{\text{Initial carrier}}{\text{Carrier in solution}}}$$

It was found by a trial experiment that crystallisation of internally formed $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ from different degrees of supersaturation was not feasible. Study on the preformed crystals was therefore carried out by the method of Khlopin¹⁰. Crystals of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared¹¹, powdered and filtered through 150 mesh in a cold room. Same quantity of powdered solid was introduced in series of L-shaped tubes containing equal volumes of 9N. H_2SO_4 impregnated with the activity in question, and shaken in the thermostat at 15.0°. A portion of the solution was taken out and the activity and thallium contents were estimated at intervals of time. Homogeneous distribution coefficient (D) was

Fig. 1. Distribution of Sc^{46} , Tl^{114} , Fe^{55+59} , Y^{90} , Bi^{210} , $\text{Eu}^{152,154}$ and Tm^{170} between $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals and its saturated solution in 9N. H_2SO_4 medium at 15°C showing the attainment of equilibrium.

Concentration of scandium, indium, iron, yttrium, bismuth, europium and thulium were 1.5×10^{-7} , 1.74×10^{-4} , 1.9×10^{-3} , 3×10^{-7} , 1.09×10^{-3} , 5.2×10^{-7} and 2.3×10^{-3} molar respectively.

————— Left hand side scale.

..... Right hand side scale.

8. L. Henderson and F. Kracek, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 738.
9. H. Doerner and W. Hoskins, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 662.
10. Khlopin and Merculova, *Doklady Akad Nauk, SSSR* 1949, 65, 861 ; 1950, 71, 689.
11. V. Fortini, *Gazz. Chim. Ital*, 1905, 35, 450.

calculated and plotted against time. In each of the cases of scandium, indium, ferric iron, europium, thulium, yttrium and bismuth used as guests equilibrium is attained at about 48 hrs (fig. 1). Solid phase was then varied and D was determined after shaking the contents for 72 hrs. Results are shown in tables and figures.

TABLE I

Coprecipitation of Tb¹⁶⁰, Tm¹⁷⁰, Sc⁴⁶, Fe⁵⁵⁺⁵⁹ and In¹¹⁴ with (NH₄)Ce(SO₄)₂·4H₂O crystals in 3N.H₂SO₄ medium at 15°.

Initial tracer conc.	% of cerium pptd.	% of tracer pptd.	D	λ
(a) 6.2×10^{-6} M. (terbium)	84.8	50.3	0.191	0.380
	73.9	37.9	0.226	0.364
	64.8	31.0	0.224	0.356
	55.6	25.2	0.269	0.358
			Average	0.364
(b) 4.2×10^{-4} M. (thulium)	80.7	21.4	0.065	0.146
	73.1	14.7	0.064	0.121
	63.6	14.2	0.095	0.152
	57.3	12.3	0.105	0.155
			Average	0.144
(c) 8.7×10^{-4} M. (,)	79.4	18.4	0.059	0.129
	70.0	12.6	0.069	0.112
	61.9	10.8	0.075	0.119
	57.6	8.7	0.079	0.125
			Average	0.122
(d) 3×10^{-3} M. (scandium)	81.3	7.6	0.024	.0471
	70.5	5.7	0.025	.0481
	65.5	4.9	0.027	.0472
	54.6	4.5	0.039	.0583
(e) 1.8×10^{-3} M. (iron-ic)	80.2	8.7	0.023	0.056
	73.2	6.6	0.025	0.052
	65.5	4.8	0.026	0.046
	54.9	3.7	0.028	0.048
(f) 1.5×10^{-3} M. (indium)	74.3	7.3	0.027	0.056
	65.8	6.8	0.033	0.065
	54.8	5.1	0.044	0.066
	46.6	5.2	0.063	0.085

N.B. In each case the contents were shaken for 24 hours.

495 mg. of cerium in 50 ml. and 4.62 g. of solid ammonium sulphate were taken in tubes already described. Extent of crystallisation of the solid phase was varied by adding different quantities of 3N.H₂SO₄.

It is of interest to mention about the procedures adopted in isolating finite amount of tetrahydrated double sulphate of scandium by breeding on corresponding thallic host at 3° having analogous composition. A specially designed experimental set up was arranged (fig. 2) so that crystallisation of the double salt, its separation from solution, drying and other operations could be made at a constant temperature (below 4°). In this set up a sintered glass bed is fixed within a sample container with a socket at the upper end and a cone at the lower end. These ends can be closed when necessary by a cone and a socket at the two ends respectively. The

FIG. 2. A SECTIONAL VIEW OF THE MAIN FEATURES OF APPARATUS USED IN THE ATTEMPT FOR ISOLATION OF TETRAHYDRATED DOUBLE SULPHATE OF SCANDIUM.

TABLE II

Distribution of Sc^{46} on preformed $(NH_4)Ti(SO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ crystals and its saturated solution in $9N.H_2SO_4$ medium at different temperatures.

Intitial conc. of scandium.	Temp. °C	Thallium in solid phase %.	Tracer in solid phase %	D
a) $1.5 \times 10^{-7}M.$	0°	50.8	49.9	0.962
		44.2	43.2	0.951
		36.5	36.0	0.978
		25.5	24.3	0.940
		Average		
*b) " "	2.5°	—	—	1.02
c) " "	5°	48.5	57.2	1.46
		37.2	48.1	1.47
		30.4	40.7	1.57
		23.4	31.5	1.50
		Average		
d) " "	8°	41.2	52.3	1.56
		36.4	47.5	1.58
		31.7	42.0	1.56
		19.0	27.2	1.59
		Average		
e) " "	10°	45.8	55.8	1.53
		37.4	49.5	1.64
		29.2	39.8	1.60
		17.7	26.0	1.63
		Average		
f) " "	15°	44.2	56.4	1.63
		37.5	49.3	1.62
		28.0	41.2	1.80
		17.9	27.8	1.76
		Average		
g) $3.6 \times 10^{-8}M$	15°	42.7	58.9	1.92
		39.2	52.9	1.76
		29.0	43.5	1.88
		25.1	36.6	1.76
		Average		

* Value of D in case of (b) was taken from fig. 1 after the attainment of equilibrium.

TABLE III

Distribution of In¹¹⁴ on preformed (NH₄)Ti(SO₄)₂.4H₂O crystals and its saturated solution in 9N.H₂SO₄ medium at different temperatures.

Initial conc. of indium	Temp. °C	Thallium in solid phase (%).	Tracer in solid phase (%).	D
a) 1.01 × 10 ⁻¹ M.	15°	48.6	11.75	0.1408
		42.05	9.7	0.1481
		36.7	7.5	0.1402
		28.3	5.8	0.1561
		Average		
b) 1.74 × 10 ⁻⁴ M	„	47.84	11.6	0.142
		44.0	9.2	0.130
		34.1	7.1	0.148
		22.4	4.0	0.144
		Average		
c) „ „	18°	48.7	15.8	0.197
		41.6	12.9	0.207
		31.2	8.8	0.211
		23.5	5.8	0.200
		Average		
d) „ „	20°	50.24	15.3	0.178
		42.6	13.95	0.216
		32.0	11.5	0.276
		23.46	8.5	0.303

N. B. Contents were shaken for 72 hours in each case.

TABLE IV

Distribution of Fe⁵⁵⁺⁵⁹ on preformed (NH₄)Ti(SO₄)₂.4H₂O crystals and its saturated solution in 9N.H₂SO₄ medium at 15°.

Initial tracer conc.	Thallium in the solid phase (%).	Tracer in the solid phase (%).	D
a) 5.7 × 10 ⁻⁴ M.	48.84	11.3	0.133
	44.14	8.7	0.121
	36.0	7.4	0.143
	26.26	4.5	0.132
	Average		
b) 1.43 × 10 ⁻³ M.	44.73	11.8	0.165
	29.5	8.2	0.165
	30.3	6.3	0.155
	25.0	5.0	0.158
	Average		
c) 1.1 × 10 ⁻¹ M.	48.38	21.2	0.287
	43.2	17.1	0.271
	35.45	13.1	0.279
	23.15	7.9	0.285
	Average		

N. B. Contents were shaken for 72 hours in each case.

lower socket is removed and placed inside a glass jacket below which is fitted a conical flask with a side tube connected to the pumping unit. Cold water from the thermostat is circulated through the jacket and this arrangement keeps the sample all along at the desired temperature. The upper end of the apparatus is connected to a long spiral copper pipe immersed in the thermostat through which dry cold air can be passed for drying the sample. The sample container can then be taken out from the cooling chamber by closing with standard joints so that neither any moisture from outside can enter nor the water vapour can escape out from inside if the substance becomes efflorescent at room temperature. The container with the

sample can be weighed as such. The sample can be dissolved without any difficulty and analysed.

Efficiency of this experimental set up was however checked up by crystallising ferric ammonium alum from its supersaturated solution in dil. H_2SO_4 and subsequently by washing and drying the crystals in the sample container. Composition of the crystals on analysis was found to correspond with the formula $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$. A sample of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ was also prepared¹² and in order to study the stability in $9N.\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ it was equilibrated for six days at 3° . Solid phase was then filtered, washed and dried in the same apparatus at 3° and analysed. Here also the solid phase found to remain unchanged. Findings derived in unknown systems were claimed to be dependable.

Preparation of the tetrahydrated double sulphate of scandium by co-crystallising with that of thallic thallium was carried out in the following way. A $9N.\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution containing 225 mg of scandium was added to nearly saturated solution of thallic sulphate in $9N.\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (15.2 gm in 100 ml) taken in a basin. A cold solution of ammonium sulphate as required by $\text{Tl}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3, \text{Sc}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \rightarrow 2(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ was then added. About 100 mg of freshly prepared $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was added as nuclei. The basin was placed in a vacuum dessicator with dehydrating arrangement and kept in thermostat at 3° . After some days when a suitable quantity of the crystals separated out, it was filtered, washed thoroughly with $9N.\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and then made acid free by washing with cold absolute ethanol at the same thermostat temperature. Crystals were then dried for about an hour by passing dry air cooled to 3° . The sample holder closed by cone and socket was then removed, weighed at room temperature and its contents were washed out with warmed dil. HCl and the solution was analysed as follows.

A portion of the solution was treated with chlorine water to prevent any reduction of thallic to thallic state and hydroxides of thallium and scandium were precipitated by passing gaseous ammonia. Precipitate was repeatedly washed with ammoniacal water till free from chloride, and sulphate was estimated in the filtrate as BaSO_4 . The hydroxide precipitate was dissolved in dil. H_2SO_4 and sulphur dioxide was added to reduce thallic thallium to thallic state which was then separated as iodide. From the solution scandium was precipitated as hydroxide, ignited as Sc_2O_3 and weighed as such. Any loss of scandium during the operation was checked by addition of Sc^{46} tracer of high specific activity. In another portion of the original solution ammonia was estimated in the usual way by distillation from the alkaline solution. Found : $\text{NH}_4^+ 3.77\%$, $\text{Sc}^{+3} 0.572\%$ (6.08 mol%), $\text{Tl}^{+3} 40.15$ (93.92 mol%), $\text{SO}_4^{-2} 40.27\%$, $\text{H}_2\text{O} 15.24\%$ (scandium was assumed to be present as $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$; and water was calculated by difference). Required for a mixture of 93.92 mol% of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 6.08 mol% of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$: $\text{NH}_4^+ 03.78\%$, $\text{Sc}^{+3} 0.574\%$, $\text{Tl}^{+3} 40.22\%$, $\text{SO}_4^{-2} 40.31\%$, $\text{H}_2\text{O} 15.11\%$.

Amount of scandium was then increased to ~14 mol% and it was allowed to cocrystallise along with $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 3° . Crystals thus obtained was filtered, washed and analysed as described previously. Found: NH_4^+ 3.86%, Sc^{+3} 1.32% (13.77 mol%), Tl^{+3} 37.6% (86.23 mol%), SO_4^{-2} 42.77%, H_2O 14.45%; required for a mixture of 86.23 mol% of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 13.77 mol% of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$: NH_4^+ 3.88%, Sc^{+3} 1.34%, Tl^{+3} 37.9%, SO_4^{-2} 41.4%, H_2O 15.48%.

Attempts were made under different experimental conditions to prepare $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ both in the pure state and also in the form of a mixture by breeding on $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, containing higher amount of scandium (above 14 mol%). Findings have been summarised in table 5.

TABLE V

A summary of preparative efforts on tetrahydrated double sulphate of scandium either through breeding on $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or in pure state under different experimental conditions.

Temperature. °C	Scandium taken	Thallium (ic) taken	Other experimental conditions	Composition of the solid phase with necessary comments.
a) 3	6. mo 1%,	94.0 mol%.	Solid ammonium sulphate was taken as required by $\text{Tl}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$, $\text{Sc}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \rightarrow 2(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$. Initial acidity was ~9N with respect to H_2SO_4 .	In both of (a) and (b) the isolated product is a mixture of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, containing 6.08 mol% and 13.77 mol% of scandium respectively.
b) 3	14.0 „	86.0 „	„	„
c) 3	pure scandium	nil	Solid ammonium sulphate was taken as required by $\text{Sc}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \rightarrow 2(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$. Initial acidity was 9N. with respect to H_2SO_4 .	The isolated product is a mixture of disulphate and trisulphate salts and some higher hydrates of unknown composition.
d) 8	„	„	„	„
e) 8	„	„	„	„
			(Cold absolute ethanol was dropwisely added till the crystallisation is complete)	
f) 14	22.7 mol %.	77.3 mol%	Solid ammonium sulphate was taken as required by $\text{Tl}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$, $\text{Sc}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 - 2(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$. Initial acidity was ~9N. with respect to H_2SO_4 .	The isolated product is a mixture of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2$.
g) 14	10.5 „	89.5 „	„	„
h) 3	50 „	50 „	„	„
i) 3	25 „	75 „	„	„
j) 14	pure scandium (2.72 gms of Sc_2O_3).	nil	2.72 gms of ammonium sulphate was taken. Initial acidity was ~1N with respect to H_2SO_4 .	The isolated product is pure $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ and is stable in 9N. H_2SO_4 at 3° .

N. B. In all the cases of (a), (b), (c), (d), (f), (g), (h) and (i) freshly prepared $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals (100 mg) was added as nuclei.

It is well known that crystallisation of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in pure state is a very difficult process as the compounds like ammonium ferric alum, trisulphato compounds and other disulphato hydrates including ferridisulphuric acid etc. separate out. An attempt was therefore made to isolate thus far unknown $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the following way. 7.72 gms of freshly prepared powdered sample of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was taken in 50 ml of 9N. H_2SO_4 containing 290 mg of iron (ic) and these were shaken for sufficient time (six days) at 15°. Solid phase was separated in the way already described and analysed. Found : NH_4^+ 3.85%, Fe^{+3} 1.35%, Tl^{+3} 38.4%, SO_4^{-2} 41.0%, H_2O 15.4%, Required for a mixture of 88.6 mol% of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 11.4 mol% of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$: NH_4^+ 3.83%, Fe^{+3} 1.36%, Tl^{+3} 38.6%, SO_4^{-2} 40.94%, H_2O 15.27% (Tl^{+3} was assumed to be present as $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the water was calculated by difference).

DISCUSSIONS

A glance at the table 1 shows that in case of both terbium and thulium as guests heterogeneous distribution factor (λ) comes out constant. Guest ions in question are therefore taken up by $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ through mixed crystal formation.

Fig.3. Relationship of λ values with reference to ionic radii^s in the distribution of $\text{Eu}^{150,154}$, Tb^{160} , Tm^{170} and Y^{91} as guests and $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host. λ in case of cerium has been taken as unity.

Fig. 3 where λ values have been plotted against ionic radii (λ values of yttrium and europium have already been determined, *vide*-previous communication¹) shows that partition values follow a decreasing trend with decrease in ionic size which is the characteristic of double salt formation in rare earth region. It can therefore be inferred that under favourable circumstances tetrahydrated double sulphate of rare earths and rare earth analogues can be isolated.

Studies with $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host and scandium, indium and ferric ion as guest showed that the partition values are very low (table-1). In spite of the low partition values a continuous increasing trend with decrease in the amount of host component has been observed in each of three systems. Conclusion can therefore be

arrived that scandium, indium and ferric ion tracers are not taken up by the host lattice in question through mixed crystal formation.

Disagreement in λ values in cases of scandium, indium and ferric iron as guests with respect to the host $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ may be either due to high solubility of the guest component in question, or the crystal parameters of the guest component may be far away from that of the host. This may not mean that scandium, indium and ferric ion would not form any tetrahydrated double sulphate. The question however can be overcome if a host component which is very soluble and whose crystal parameters are also different, be chosen. With this object in view $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was taken as host and distribution studies with different tracers were undertaken.

A glance at the tables (2, 3, 4) show that the homogeneous distribution factor (D) comes out constant both at tracer level and finite concentration of the guest ions. Scandium, indium and ferric iron are therefore taken up by $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ through mixed crystal formation. Conclusion thus arrived at that tetrahydrated double sulphates of scandium, indium and ferric iron analogous in composition to that of thallic thallium do exist. In case of scandium, a study of transition temperature¹⁸ was taken recourse to through the measurement of distribution factors. It has been found that there is a break in the neighbourhood of 5°, whereas solubility of the host component at different temperatures runs a

Fig. 4. Curve A. Study of distribution coefficient (D) of Sc^{46} as guest and $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host at different temperatures. Curve B. solubility of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 9N. H_2SO_4 at different temperatures.

— Left hand side scale
 - - - - Right hand side scale

Fig. 5. Freundlich adsorption isotherm on carrying of (A) yttrium, (B) terbium and (C) thulium on preformed $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. x , amount of yttrium, terbium or thulium carried (g/l). c , concentration of yttrium, terbium or thulium remaining in solution (g/l), m , amount of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (g/l).

Initial conc. of the guest ions: Yttrium $\sim 1.32 \times 10^{-2} M$
 Terbium $\sim 0.8 \times 10^{-2} M$
 Thulium $\sim 0.66 \times 10^{-2} M$

smooth straight line course (fig.4). This infers that the tetrahydrated double sulphate of scandium cannot exist above 5°.

Fig. 6. Freundlich adsorption isotherm on carrying of (A) thulium (B) bismuth and (C) yttrium on preformed $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. x , amount of thulium, bismuth or yttrium carried (g/l). c , concentration of thulium, bismuth or yttrium remaining in solution (g/l); m , amount of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (g/l).

Initial conc. of the guest ions : Thulium $\sim 1.9 \times 10^{-5} M$
 Bismuth $\sim 1.09 \times 10^{-5} M$
 Yttrium $\sim 3.0 \times 10^{-7} M$

Fig. 7. Freundlich adsorption isotherm on carrying of (A) europium and (B) terbium by preformed $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. x , amount of europium or terbium carried (g/l). c , concentration of europium or terbium remaining in solution (g/l), m , amount of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (g/l).

Initial conc. of the guest ions : Europium $\sim 5.2 \times 10^{-7} M$
 Terbium $\sim 6.2 \times 10^{-6} M$

Uptake in case of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host and rare earths like europium, terbium and thulium and rare earth analogues like yttrium and bismuth as guests followed an adsorption pattern (fig. 5, 6 & 7). Absence of uptake through mixed crystal formation in these cases may probably be due to the difference in crystal parameters of the host component as a whole, though the ionic radii of the guest ions in question are very near to the ionic radius of thallic thallium.

The change in partition values with respect to the concentration of the guest component in solution has been studied in considerable details. In table-2 and 3, it has been shown that increase of concentration of scandium or indium does not affect the partition values whereas increase in the concentration of ferric ion (table-4) raises the partition value to a considerable extent. The system in case of ferric ion as guest behaved as molecular mixed crystal formation as was shown by Khlopin¹⁰ in the uptake of Ra by LaF_3 . Question naturally arises whether this particular uptake belongs to the group of anomalous mixed crystal formation. This issue was examined by taking finite quantity of ferric ion and equilibrating with the host for sufficient time, after which the solid phase was analysed. The solid product isolated was found to be the mixture of two tetrahydrated double sulphates with 11.4 mol% of iron (vide experimental section). The partition value at this concentration of ferric ion was

also found to be near about the same (table-4). This gives the evidence that host and the guest component have the same chemical composition. It should therefore be regarded as the case of normal mixed crystal formation.

Increase of partition values with increase in concentration of the guest ion may in this case be due to the presence of different complex ferric ions in solution. Existence of $\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_3^{-3}$ ions are well known. Ionic radii of Tl^{+3} and Fe^{+3} ions are far away from each other. It is quite likely that a saturated solution of $\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$ ion cannot fully stabilise the corresponding $\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$ ion. concentration of $\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$ ion increases with increase in ferric ion concentration and partition value also rises accordingly. It will not be far from truth if we assume that $\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$ ion exchanges with $\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$ ion of the host component. Free Fe^{+3} ion probably does not play any role in the exchange process. But the situation in case of scandium and indium as guests is however different. Ionic radii of these two guest ions are much closer to that of thallic thallium and activity coefficient ratio of tracer to carrier may be taken as unity. As a result, partition values do not undergo any change over a wide range of guest ion concentration. It may therefore be inferred that scandium and indium bear close chemical resemblance with thallic thallium in the system under study. From the observations it can also be assumed that uptake of scandium and indium followed the same behaviour like that of ferric iron.

It should be mentioned that the distribution coefficient of indium as guest has been studied at different temperatures. In table 3, it has been shown that the partition values at 18° is somewhat increased than those obtained at 15° . But at 20° the values follow a gradually increasing trend with decrease in the amount of solid phase and the uptake followed an absorption pattern. This is due to the earlier observation¹⁴ that the host component itself decomposes at 20° . Transition temperature of the host component in question therefore lies between 18° and 20° .

A glance at the table 5 (a and b) will show that it has been possible to prepare mixtures of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ containing 6.08 mol% and 13.77 mol% of scandium respectively. $\text{Tl} : \text{Sc}$ ratio in both the cases was found to be almost the same as was initially taken in the solution. Partition values were therefore near about unity which was also found in the distribution studies with scandium as guest from tracer to finite concentration (table—1). This success in the isolation of 13.77 mol% of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ through breeding on $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ not only sets forth evidence on the existence of tetrahydrated double sulphate of scandium, but it also serves as a positive evidence that in all our distribution measurements scandium has isomorphously replaced the thallic thallium in the solid phase probably as $\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$ ions.

In our attempts of preparing $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 3° , the isolated product was found to be a mixture of di- and trisulphate salts and some higher hydrates still

14. Rössler, *Jour. Prakt. Chem.*, 1873, 7, (2), 18.

unknown to us (table 5). With the view that $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ may also be stable even above 5° , similar attempts were made at 8° . Here also we got a mixture of ill defined chemical composition. Two more attempts were then made to cocrystallise the mixture of double salts in question at 14° by breeding upon $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ taking initially 23 Mol% and 10.5 mol% of scandium respectively. This resulted in the formation of a mixture of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2$. Conclusion can thus be arrived at that the tetrahydrated double sulphate of scandium is not stable above 5° . Temperature was then fixed at 3° and similar attempts were made by taking initially 50 mol% and 25 mol% of scandium respectively. It is interesting that here also we got a mixture of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ and in fact about 76 mol% of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ has been separated in the solid phase only when 25 mol% of scandium was initially taken. This shows that crystals of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ can accommodate only upto ~ 14 mol% of a scandium having analogous chemical composition (below 4°). Formation of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ in presence of larger amount of thallic thallium may be due to the fact that $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is metastable with respect to the anhydrous form, even below the transition temperature. Most salient point to be noted is that upto about 82 mol% of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ was separated along with $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ from 9N. H_2SO_4 solution, whereas $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ could not be prepared from 9N. H_2SO_4 solution as such. This anhydrous salt was however found to be stable in 9N. H_2SO_4 even after equilibration for six days at 3° and is less soluble ($\sim 1/5$ th) than $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ under identical experimental conditions. This seems to be the reason why the anhydrous form always appeared before the tetrahydrated crystallises out in all our attempts of preparation of the pure tetrahydrated double sulphate of scandium and also the mixture of two tetrahydrates in question containing higher amount of scandium (14 mol%). Mechanism may be such that $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ breeds over the nucleus of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ upto a concentration of 14 mol% of scandium in solution and with continuous growth, the scandium compound decomposes to anhydrous double sulphate which is the stable form. This then acts as nuclei and the reaction becomes unidirectional, as a result of which even when only 25 mol% of scandium was initially taken in solution, 76 mol% of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ separated in the solid phase. However, this anhydrous form does not in any way bring in any change in the composition of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Tl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ which remains all along side by side. Also, it may so happen that $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ takes up most of the scandium incorporated in the thallic thallium host as the highest concentration of scandium first resides in the surface of the thallic host and as soon as a portion is converted to the anhydrous form the rest undergoes successive transformations. Tetrahydrated double sulphate of scandium thus seems to be metastable with respect to the anhydrous double sulphate just as $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is metastable¹⁵ with respect to $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or like orthorhombic and monoclinic $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ¹⁶. Isolation of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{Sc}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is therefore a matter of problem in connection with the isolation of metastable phases.

15. S. Glasstone "Text Book of Physical Chemistry" 1956, p-773.

16. C. R. Bury, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2538.

It has already been pointed out that rare earths and rare earth analogues like yttrium and bismuth are carried out by the cerous host through mixed crystal formation. Our study therefore gives evidence on the existence of another group of tetrahydrated double sulphates having same crystalline form but different parameters. Tetrahydrated double sulphates of rare earths and rare earth analogues like yttrium and bismuth fall in one side and those of aluminium, scandium, indium, thallic thallium and ferric iron belong to another group. Uptake through mixed crystal formation does not take place between members of these two groups both at finite and tracer concentration which have been shown in considerable details with some of the guest ions. It is thus evident that all the trivalent elements (cations) are expected to form tetrahydrated double sulphates. But the situation is different in case of alums where formation of alums are restricted to only a few. Formation of tetrahydrated double sulphate can therefore be regarded as a general characteristic of trivalent cations.

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